

A Feasibility Study for inclusion of Ethics and Social issues in Engineering and Design Coursework in Australia

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports on a feasibility study on including ethics and social issues in the current curriculum of a school of engineering and information technology in an Australian university. The study has three goals: first, to understand the current status of inclusion of ethics and social issues in engineering courses. Second, to understand the willingness of staff within the school to include ethics and societal issues in their courses. Third, to understand the opportunities and challenges for inclusion of ethical and societal issues in the coursework. Our methods include interviews with school staff and subject matter experts as well as analyses of textual artifacts such as course outlines, course readings, student assignments, and accreditation reports. The analysis of textual artifacts runs partially via an automated text analyzer that search for words that have ethical connotation, such as safety, responsibility, privacy, harm, etcetera in the dataset of course materials. A manual (human) analysis of the coursework was done for those courses that give insufficient results in the automated text analyzer. We looked for opportunities to include ethics and societal issues in coursework. The conclusion is that there is general consensus amongst staff that ethics and societal issues deserve more attention in the school. At the same time, there is concern that including ethics and societal issues takes away valuable teaching time for technical material. There is preference for an integrated way of ethics teaching, rather than one separate engineering ethics course.

1 INTRODUCTION

What constitutes a good engineer? What are the standards of excellence for a technical designer? Our research responds to the increasing demand from society for engineers that are socially and ethically responsible, especially in the face of current technological developments such as autonomous vehicles and AI [1]. The way engineers and designers are trained, not merely in their technical skills but also in their understanding of societal impact and ethical aspects of the things they design, may tacitly or explicitly influence design choices. Design choices that lead to concrete products or services may impact our societies for better or worse. Famous examples include Moses' low hanging bridges in New York that prevented the poor, travelling by bus, to visit the Long Island beaches, exacerbating socioeconomic inequality [2]. The recent collapse of the apartment building in Miami, Florida [1], is another example of the importance of nurturing and fostering ethically and socially responsible engineers. To better understand the role of ethics in engineering and design education, we conducted a feasibility study to probe the UNSW Canberra SEIT (School of Engineering and Information Technology) curriculum on where engineering and design students have space to critically reflect on and creatively play with societal and ethical aspects of their coursework. An explorative feasibility study in the context of curriculum improvement in higher education is a proven way to understand the

potential for embedding a new element into a curriculum [3]. Numerous studies exist in the field of engineering ethics education, each stressing a different aspect of the challenge, such as cultural contexts [4], pointing to a decision focused method [5], addressing ethical and social aspects in AI education [6] or advocating a broader understanding of the task of the engineer [7]. For example, Taebi and Kastenber [8] report on their experience on setting up engineering ethics education in UC Berkeley. They identified institutional and academic hurdles during their implementation phase. Our aim was to explore these and other hurdles and opportunities to systematically map the current approach in SEIT regarding social and ethical reflection in engineering and design courses. We were interested in understanding the opportunities for students to think through the effects of design choices on ethical issues in the short and long run (e.g. acquiring and recycling of used materials), on safety in use, on opportunities for transparency and honesty in functionalities, and social issues, such as: how do design choices constrain or enable patterns of social behavior, and how accessible and affordable does a technology become for certain groups in society? We agree with Grunwald (2000) [9] that the role of ethics in technology development is not equally important in all subjects of engineering and technology education, so one may question the degree and kind of ethical and social reflection that is required in certain areas of technology development or engineering subfields. Mapping the current situation in SEIT helps us better understand where there is space for ethical reflection and where not. Taebi and Kastenber [8] furthermore note that faculty members from engineering departments are often the ones who can best relate to and identify the ethical aspects of their own specific field of engineering, hence our justification for interviewing staff in SEIT. Since the Australian context is rather specific [10][11][12], and as engineering education in Australia is accredited by professional bodies (Engineers Australia (EA)), we included Engineers Australia as participants in our interview round. This research is essential, as it fills a gap in knowledge around to what degree ethics can and should inform the engineering curriculum in UNSW Canberra's SEIT.

2 METHODOLOGY

This project used a qualitative research methodology, deploying the following data collection method/s:

1. Semi-structured interviews with SEIT staff and subject matter experts
2. Scoping, coding, analysing of existing textual artifacts (course materials such as syllabus, EA accreditation report, blank assignments, Moodle sites).

This two-fold methodology (data gathering through document analysis and interviews) satisfied our aim to understand the current situation of ethical and social reflection in engineering and design courses in SEIT and helped us understand the opportunities or hindrances to enhance this.

SEIT staff were selected for interviews through the UNSW Canberra Handbook for students, which lists teaching staff per course. Courses that were more inclined towards ethical aspects such as security, data handling and automation were chosen

along with theoretically intensive courses such as engineering mechanics or radar technology. This was done keeping in mind the research aim: to capture insight from key insiders on where ethics can and cannot be implemented within the course structure. Subject matter experts on engineering ethics were selected from the professional networks of the researchers. All interviews were conducted online.

For the coursework materials analysis, we developed a simple regex based matching algorithm in Python, against ethics related keywords (e.g. honesty, trust, responsibility, danger, harm) and then manually checked those sentences, to find spaces where ethics is already incorporated or if there is room for the same. Regex stands for Regular Expressions, which are a sequence of characters that specify search patterns in a text. They have been developed in theoretical computer science for use in keyword find or find-and-replace algorithms.

3 RESULTS

In the following subsections, we present the results from interviews with SEIT Staff and subject matter experts as well as the coursework analysis. We interviewed a total of six SEIT staff members and three subject matter experts (SMEs). We coded the data collected in the interviews, and then clustered the codes into broader categories they fell into. From the clusters, seven themes came up. These themes are discussed in the following subsections. Our general observation was that five out of six staff members were in favour of incorporating ethics in the curriculum, while one staff member was not in favor, as they thought there was not enough space and necessity to incorporate ethics in the curriculum. We will now systematically address our interview findings based on the clusters that were made. The second part of the results section reports the automated and manual coursework analysis.

3.1 Interviews:

What is ethics according to SEIT Staff

Interviewed staff mentioned a range of aspects to be “ethics”, from values such as honesty, personal morals, to the professional aspects of taking responsibility, decision making and dealing with complexity. A relationship between ethics and systems engineering came up especially when staff related ethics to the professional aspects of taking responsibility and ensuring verifiability. For example, a staff member with a systems engineering background said, “engineering is often about design and when you design, the choices you make are related to stakeholder requirements, and those stakeholder requirements are strongly related to ethical aspects.”

The importance of ethics in engineering

SEIT staff mostly pointed out that ethics is important for engineers. They mentioned the impact of technology and the role engineers play in every aspect of the current society, hence the importance of teaching political, financial and intent related aspects in engineering. The staff also related the importance of ethics in engineering to safety, privacy and preserving lives. Furthermore, that technology can be used for both good and bad was often mentioned. All SMEs seemed to agree that a greater awareness of

ethics in engineering is required. This was mostly attributed to the growing responsibility attributed to engineers who are today working in so many interdisciplinary sectors.

Possibilities to incorporate ethics in SEIT course content

When asked whether the staff think they can incorporate ethics in the curriculum, we were met with mostly positive responses either in terms of an intention to incorporate more of ethics in the curriculum, or ethics already being incorporated in the curriculum. Staff 3 for example, said that “[Ethics] is a very important aspect of the Master space postgraduate program. We have some world leading space ethicists, a very multidisciplinary team...Ethics is at the very core of what we are trying to build.” Other staff members mentioned ethics is being implemented via role-modelling and inviting top-level executives and through teaching how to comply with professional codes in applied settings.

Barriers to incorporation of ethics in SEIT course content

Staff thought it less feasible to incorporate ethics into coursework in theoretically or mathematically intensive courses. Staff 3, for example, mentioned that “For me it’s easy, but for someone who teaches fluid mechanics, would maybe not be as positive.” Lack of expertise to teach ethics is also a common concern among staff. However, most staff were willing to put in the effort to improve upon their expertise in teaching ethics. Another concern is the lack of time, which results in staff being concerned about having to compromise the technical content of the course to be able to include ethics, such as Staff 6 said, “If specifically asked, we will have to take something out from the course, which means technical skills get taken out. Are we developing engineers with good technical skills or good soft skills?” As this quote indicates, some staff consider ethics a soft skill. Some think that it can be obtained later during the job, or they think of ethics in terms of personal or private values and that teaching ethics is pointless. Furthermore, some think that students might not be interested in ethics teachings. Other staff who have already successfully implemented or are trying to implement ethics in curriculum did not bring up this lack of interest from students. According to the SMEs, one of the barriers in incorporating ethics in an engineering curriculum, is the challenge in explaining ethics to engineering students who lack foundational knowledge. Some SMEs pointed out the importance of philosophical knowledge of ethics while others stressed the need for its application to engineering.

Incentives for incorporation of ethics in SEIT curriculum

Internal motivation and value based incentives, in terms of awareness amongst engineers about honesty and their general responsibility towards society was evident in most of our staff interviews. Another equally important incentive that came up in our interviews was accreditation. Both Engineers Australia and Australian Computer Society are responsible for accrediting engineering institutions in Australia. The staff raised concerns about the recent accreditation visits by EA and the resulting discussions at all organizational levels to incorporate ethics in the curriculum. SME 3 pointed towards an upcoming increased relevance of ethics in EA and International

Engineering Alliance (IEA) competency standards. They said, “International Engineering Alliance has updated their professional competency terms with an increased relevance of ethics. EA is aligned with IEA competency and therefore accreditation requirements will increase.”

How to incorporate ethics and social issues in SEIT curriculum

Staff raised concerns about a lack of direction on how to implement ethics in the curriculum. Staff 4 mentioned that “we want to do it, but don’t know how to do it” and, likewise, Staff 5 said, “There is definitely space for [incorporating ethics] but the challenge is how to fit it in naturally.” Most SEIT staff interviewed think that a coherent integration would be the best way to incorporate ethics in the curriculum. Another relevant method that staff positively mentioned in interviews was a case-study based teaching of ethics, which is expected to be interesting for students. Staff 1 for example, said, “The thing is that it is a bit easy for me because I teach cyber, which is a hot topic, so new set of use cases all the time, and most of them have some or the other ethical aspect in them.” An ethics course may be perceived as a box to tick, as Staff 5 mentioned, “A separate class would feel like a box to tick. It somehow needs to be authentically integrated into the project and I don’t know how.” Ironically, a forced implementation of ethics is also not preferred, as Staff 6 said, “If specifically asked, we will have to take something out from the course... If at the end of the day you NEED to teach it to engineers, then engineers should be doing it.”

Who should include ethics and social issues in SEIT courses?

In general, SEIT staff showed a preference towards ethics being closely integrated within the curriculum and that it should be internal SEIT staff teaching it. Some staff expressed concern about potential lack of respect from engineering students for teachers from non-engineering faculty. However, some staff also had concerns about their lack of expertise in ethics, as mentioned in section 4.4. To mitigate this, some staff suggested the involvement of a multidisciplinary team. Staff 5, for example, said, “I am from a very technical background where things are clear but with ethics there is not necessarily wrong or right answers, although this is where humanities comes in to weigh.” SMEs mentioned that commitment from the school leadership and support from course coordinators is vital for the success of enhancing ethics in engineering education.

3.2 Coursework Analysis

Most courses returned meaningful results through the text analyzer algorithm, which looked for ethically charged words in the text. The last two courses listed below and indicated with “*” did not return sufficient results via the analyzer, because of the document formats, so they were manually analysed by the researchers.

Course on Big Data and Decision Analytics for Security - This course takes a case-study based approach to ethics education. It incorporates readings such as “Losing Humanity: The Case Against Killer Robots”, and “Discriminating algorithms: 5 times AI showed Prejudice”, which cover ethical aspects such as human rights, moral and

social responsibility, value of life and risk assessment. However, it is important that these aspects are not only introduced through readings but also explicitly discussed from an ethical perspective rather than merely a security breach perspective.

Course on Software Security Lifecycle - This course refers to the complete software development lifecycle, and therefore refers to notions of responsibility and verifiability. These notions however are not exactly emphasised from an ethical perspective. In other words, failures are interpreted from a pragmatic or economic point of view, without elaborating on how a software development lifecycle can fail in an ethical sense through its effects on society. There is room for discussion about stakeholder involvement, which is important for determining societal issues in design, as well as the ethical importance of the end-of-lifecycle: what are the risks if the software becomes outdated? Points for ethical elaboration exist in the security development lifecycle, where attention for threats, privacy, responsibility could be broadened.

Course on Computers and Security - Ethics is discussed in the first lecture of the course in a very explicit manner, under the heading of “Ethics and Cyber Ethics.” It discusses the importance of ethics to computer security professionals. The course often mentions security, rights and legal procedures and discusses the ethics of professional organisations such as the International Information System Security Certification Consortium and that of the Computer Ethics Institute. However, the course does not go into the details of ethics further down in the syllabus. There is room to mention ethics when discussing various aspects and case studies related to cyber security.

*Principles of Electrical Engineering** - This technical course has very limited opening to discuss ethical issues, but there are opportunities to discuss environmental effects or safety aspects of electrical design choices. For example, controllers used in the automotive industry where it is important to get controls and timings right due to potential harms in braking, steering or airbags. An environmentally relevant issue relates to power consumptions in circuits, which can be optimized via smart switching methods and smart use of transformers.

*Cyber Offence: Threats and Opportunities** - This short course mainly focusses on cybersecurity. Given its topic, it includes methods of creating safe software and preventing cyber-attacks. It therefore emphasises on ethical keywords such as legal, illegal, safety and security. The course however approaches these aspects from a purely technical perspective and there is indeed more room for mentioning ethical and societal aspects using case examples.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

A majority of the interviewed SEIT Staff was in favour of including ethics into the SEIT curriculum in a more systematic manner. But this conclusion should be considered in light of two considerable limitations of our study. First, that our sample size of six staff

members is small and not representative of the entire teaching staff in the school (approximately 90 staff members). Second, this majority inclination towards incorporating ethics and social issues in engineering and design coursework does not quantitatively imply a major support for it in the school at large, since staff that are not interested in ethics and social issues in engineering courses, are less likely to participate in research that explores these issues. Low interest and participation, pertaining to the undervalued perception of interdisciplinary research and the lack of incentive and organisational support on behalf of the institution, was also encountered by Taebi et. al.,[8] in running the first edition of a graduate engineering ethics course at UC Berkley.

Skinner et. al.[12], argued that engineering ethics is a special case of professional ethics and this is in line with what the majority of SEIT staff reported, together with often mentioned honesty and personal morals. Furthermore, we could see traces of the microethical model (cf. Martin et al) in SEIT staffs' understanding of ethics in engineering. A microethical model is "characterised by a strong emphasis on the individual responsibility of engineers" [13]. This was evident, for example, from the importance of an increased attention towards existing EA code of ethics that was pointed out in the interviews, by SEIT staff.

For most SMEs, on the other hand, the understanding of ethics in engineering was directed towards macroethics model, which, according to Martin et.al [13], looks at the engineering profession as a whole and the profession's responsibility towards development and society. This distinction between macro-and micro-ethics is further reflected in our interviews, as SEIT staff were a lot more inclined towards interweaving ethics in the curriculum compared to SMEs who thought having a separate course could play a role in laying the foundation and explaining ethics in much more detail from a more philosophical standpoint.

The way SEIT staff think about ethics in relation to engineering and design covers most, but not all content areas of engineering ethics education identified by Martin et al.[13]. There is awareness of responsibility, sustainability, professional ethics, societal context, value sensitive design, business studies and military applications, while less or no mention was made of health and safety, legislation, academic and research integrity or ethical theories.

One of the most popular methods of teaching engineering ethics[13][14] which was often mentioned in our interviews, is to use case studies. Cases are one of the three general models of teaching engineering as identified by Herkert [15]. Case studies can be incorporated in all coursework without much effort. A general approach is to decide upon the ethical goals related to a particular subject and then carefully choose cases. This also ensures that the incorporation of ethics is interesting for students as it is related to their own areas of study, as had been pointed out by many staff and SMEs. Furthermore, an interesting observation from some of our staff interviews was how they related ethics to a systems engineering approach and to the ideas of responsibility, professional conduct and verifiability. A promising approach to

incorporating ethics within an engineering curriculum is the VASE approach [16][17], which adds a values theory step to the pre-existing steps in a design thinking approach. This added step of values theory is targeted towards naming and teaching specific values and approaches to ethics and then relating them to values in design. Studies such as one by Lee et. al. [18], have shown how systems engineering approach can be moulded towards a human-centered/value sensitive design approach. We suggest that the VASE approach[16][17], in combination with systems engineering and value sensitive design [18] could lead to a well-rounded incorporation of ethics into something that engineers and software developers are already studying. Further research would indeed be required to come up with the exact steps of this implementation.

Although we may tentatively conclude that SEIT staff favours that ethics implementation is done by the SEIT staff, research suggests that implementation of ethics benefits from multidisciplinary attention, and it is important to have the say of philosophers and social scientists when designing it within the curriculum. Furthermore, as Skinner et. al. [12] point out, the inclusion of a formal course on ethics is not well received by all the school's staff. There is also "suspicion among the faculty of such interdisciplinary material 'diluting' the technical education of engineers" (ibid). It is therefore important to develop an understanding that teaching ethics will not take away the core theoretical engineering background but rather enhance it, if it is done in a coherent manner. It could be the university administration's responsibility to help incorporate ethics in the curriculum in a way which ensures the engineering topics are covered while including ethical and social issues. It is important for all levels of the institution to be actively involved for a successful implementation of ethics in engineering curriculum. Finally, it is important to pay attention to the cultural, educational, academic and life-experience based diversity within the student body and its effects on how a course on ethics is received by the students [12]. Engineering students may not be naturally interested in ethics, and, Skinner's[12] findings are promising, as they conclude that "students were initially suspicious, but they move beyond it over the weeks and find it liberating for their imaginations."

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